

SCIENCE MATRIX 2000: THE FUSION OF THE DIGITAL AND THE REAL IN CONTEMPORARY SCIENTIFIC PRACTICE*

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ABSTRACT

Are we on the verge of a new Renaissance? Like the Renaissance of the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries, this one is deeply connected with a revolution in information technology, however heralding to a “Posthuman” era in which human being becomes seamlessly articulated with intelligent machines. The fusion of digital and physical reality pervades our everyday life and the practice of science. Experience of materiality and our notions of the real are deeply tied to technologies that affect how we experience space and time and how we use our bodies. New computer-based media, the development of “smart devices” and agents that interact with us constantly are reshaping the channels of our experience, transforming our conception of the “real,” redefining what we mean by “community,” and some would maintain, what we mean by our “selves”. The result of such a revolution in scientific fields like Biomedicine and Biology in a broader sense may be the relocation of the lab to the industrial park.

Key words: posthuman renaissance; technoscience; “digital and real”; experience; contemporary scientific practice.

CIÊNCIA “MATRIX 2000”: A FUSÃO DO DIGITAL E DO REAL NA PRÁTICA CIENTÍFICA CONTEMPORÂNEA

Estamos no limiar de uma nova Renascença? Como a renascença dos séculos quatorze e quinze, a presente encontra-se em íntima conexão com uma revolução na tecnologia da informação, embora anunciando uma era “pós-humana” na qual o ser humano torna-se inteiramente articulado com máquinas inteligentes. A fusão da realidade digital e física permeia nossa vida diária e a prática científica. A experiência da materialidade e nossas noções do real estão intimamente ligadas a tecnologias que afetam o modo como experienciamos o tempo e o espaço e usamos nossos corpos. Novos meios de comunicação baseados no computador, o desenvolvimento

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de *smart devices* e agentes que interagem conosco constantemente estão transformando nossa noção do “real”, redefinindo o que entendemos por “comunidade” e, dizem alguns, o que entendemos por “nós mesmos”. O resultado de tal revolução, em campos como a Biomedicina e a Biologia num sentido amplo, pode ser a transferência do laboratório para o parque industrial.

Palavras-chave: renascimento pós-humano; tecnociência; “digital e real”; experiência; prática científica contemporânea.

I am intrigued by the notion that we are on the verge of a new Renaissance, which like the Renaissance of the fourteenth and fifteenth centuries is deeply connected with a revolution in information technology. That most celebrated Renaissance is frequently heralded as connected with the birth of Humanism. I sympathize with several contemporary theorists who characterize our Renaissance as heralding a Posthuman era in which human being becomes seamlessly articulated with intelligent machines. In the posthuman, there are no demarcations between bodily existence and computer simulation, between cybernetic mechanism and biological organism.¹

Let’s face it, a minimal condition for some sort of new, “post” human condition would certainly be a fundamental shift in our notions of material reality. My intention here is to explore some of the pathways through which a so-called post-human future might come about. Experience of materiality and our notions of the real are deeply tied to technologies that affect how we experience space and time and how we use our bodies. Changes in these technologies have a profound impact on our sense of materiality and of the real. Among the pathways I will point to where changes in our experiences of space and time are being packaged—where our senses are literally being reconfigured—are products of the military-entertainment complex.

But first consider the following clips from the popular media.

These clips from a recent Intel Pentium II commercial—now already superseded by the Pentium III—and the box office smash from last spring, *The Matrix*, suggest that we are becoming immersed in a growing repertoire of computer-based media for creating, distributing and interacting with digitized versions of the world. You may think that these are media-created fantasies rather than the hard stuff needed to have an impact on material reality sufficient for ushering in something as momentous as “the posthuman.” But I would urge that in numerous areas of our daily activities, we are witnessing a drive toward fusion of digital and physical reality not altogether unlike that depicted in these clips; not the replacement of the real by a hyperreal—the obliteration of a referent and its replacement by a model without origin or reality—as Baudrillard predicted, but a new playing field of ubiquitous computing in which wearable computers, independent computational agent-artifacts,

¹N. Katherine Hayles, *How We Became Posthuman: Virtual Bodies in Cybernetics, Literature, and Informatics* (Chicago; University of Chicago Press, 1999), p. 2-3.

and material objects are all part of the landscape. To paraphrase William Gibson's character Case in *Neuromancer*, "data is being made flesh."² New computer-based media are reshaping the channels of our experience, transforming our conception of the "real," redefining what we mean by "community," and some would maintain, what we mean by our "selves."³

As we come to entrust more of our lives to internet communications—from our email to class-room interactions and our finances—and as we spend more time in virtual, electronic space, our notions of materiality and reality will inevitably change. But networked communications are only the first outward signs of the posthuman genesis scenario I have in mind. A transformation of the sort we are discussing will require the cooperation of many different media interacting with us constantly rather than during the sporadic occasion when we look up information or send a message. A sign that such a more persistent medialization of this sort is indeed occurring is the rapid fusion of the digital and the real taking place less obviously in personal digital assistants, our cell phones and Palm Pilots (about to become wearable servers), that accompany us throughout the day. The sign is more clearly perceptible perhaps in technologies such as web-based personal shopping assistants that learn our preferences and then crawl the web in search of software upgrades, information, and commodities that define us as consumers of information.

Current research and development efforts to embed information technologies in the world around us, in objects other than communications devices, offers another domain ripe with suggestions about this future path for the fusion of digital and real. For a generation we have been used to thinking of the computer as the symbol of the information revolution, but one way to think about our present stage within this revolution is that the computer is in fact disappearing. If developments funded by the military research agencies such as DARPA at several research universities and at

²William Gibson, *Neuromancer*, p. 91.

³For discussions of computer-mediated communication and computational sciences see: See Richard Mark Friedhoff and William Benzon, *The Second Computer Revolution: Visualization*, New York: W.H. Freeman, 1989. Other important discussions are in *Information Technology and the Conduct of Research: The User's View*, Report of the Panel on Information Technology and the Conduct of Research, National Academy of Sciences, 1989. B.H. McCormack, T.A. DiFanti, and M.D. Brown, *Visualization in Scientific Computing*, NSF Report, published as a special issue of *Computer Graphics*, Vol. 21 (6) (1987). An equally impressive survey is the special issue on computational physics in *Physics Today*, October, 1987. See especially the articles by Norman Zambusky, "Grappling with Complexity," *ibid.*, p. 25-27; Karl-Heinz A. Winkler, *et al.*, "A Numerical Laboratory," *ibid.*, p. 28-37; Martin Karplus, "Molecular Dynamics Simulations of Proteins," *ibid.*, p. 68-72. For a consideration of computer-mediated communication and computational science in relation to theory, see Timothy Lenoir and Christophe Lécuyer, "Visions of Theory: Fashioning Molecular Biology as an Information Science," in M. Norton Wise, ed., *Growing Explanations*, Princeton: Princeton University Press (in press). For computer-mediated communication and notions of the self see: Sherry Turkel, *Life on the Screen: Identity in the Age of the Internet*, New York: Simon & Shuster, 1995, especially chapter 7, p. 177-209, and Chapter 10, p. 255-270; Brian Rotman, "Going Parallel: Beside Oneself," 1996 <<http://www-leland.stanford.edu/class/history204i/Rotman/Beside/top.html>

organizations like Xerox PARC come to pass, that large box we are used to staring into all day will vanish. In its place will be a world filled with special purpose chips, “smart” devices, and agents that interact with us constantly. These agents and devices will not sit on our desktops, but rather will be embedded in wearable microdevices and implants, leading to a world of ubiquitous computing.

Since 1996, for instance, the DARPA Smart Modules program has been developing and demonstrating novel ways of combining sensors, microprocessors, and communications in lightweight, low-power, modular packages that offer war fighters and small fighting units new methods to enhance their situational awareness and effectively control their resources on the battlefield. Smart modules are integrated into personal and portable information products that sense, compile, analyze, display, compare, store, process, and transmit information. The resulting products create opportunities to exploit data-rich battlefield environments at the individual war fighter level. Instead of the normally limited set of information resources at the disposal of the individual war fighter (maps, compasses, hand-held global positioning systems) and limited connectivity (primarily voice radio) to information infrastructures, Smart Modules are artifacts that allow individuals to better perceive their environment (see, hear, and feel the electromagnetic spectrum), augment their ability to remember and make decisions through use of electronic devices, and provide mechanisms for connection to wireless distributed data networks. Modular information products are part of clothing, worn on the belt, or put into a pocket. These products will capitalize on current rapid developments in micro electromechanical systems, head mounted and small direct-view displays, optoelectronics, integrated sensors and video modules, energy storage, and low-power electronics.

DARPA’s “smart matter” programs go beyond the wearable modular communication devices and information systems described above. Smart Matter research is based in large part on MEMS (micro electromechanical systems), very small sensors and actuators that are etched into silicon or other media using photolithography-based techniques. Integrated with computation, these sensors and actuators form a bridge between the virtual and physical worlds, enabling structures to dynamically respond to conditions in their environment. Smart materials and structures mimic the natural world where animals and plants have the clear ability to adapt to their environment in real time. Designers and promoters of these “biomimetic” technologies dream about the possibilities of such materials and structures in the man-made world, engineering structures operating at the very limit of their performance envelopes and to their structural limits without fear of exceeding either. “Smart” structures could give maintenance engineers a full report on their performance history, as well as the location of any defect as it occurs. Furthermore, that same structure could be given the ability to counteract unwanted or potentially dangerous conditions such as excessive vibration or the capacity to self-repair.

THE FUSION OF THE DIGITAL AND THE REAL: EXAMPLES FROM BIOMEDICINE

The research developments I have sketched above seem plausible, but they are not yet everyday realities. Before turning to the role of agents such as what I am calling the military entertainment complex in reshaping our world I want to consider some examples from the biomedical sciences where a fusion of digital and real is indeed becoming an everyday experience. The first example concerns the role of modeling in science and the way it is transforming medicine to a predictive science.

THE VIRTUAL SURGEON—COMPUTER-ASSISTED SURGERY

In the past decade computers have entered the operating room to assist physicians in realizing a dream they've pursued ever since Claude Bernard: to make medicine both experimental and predictive. The emerging field of computer-assisted surgery offers a dramatic change from the days of individual heroic surgeons. Soon surgeons will no longer boldly improvise modestly preplanned scripts, adjusting in the operating room on the peculiar case at hand. Increasingly, to perform surgery surgeons must use extensive 3D modeling tools to generate a predictive model, the basis for a simulation that will become a software surgical interface. This interface will guide the surgeon in performing the procedure.

THE MINIMALLY INVASIVE SURGERY REVOLUTION

These developments in surgery date back to the 1970s when the first widely successful endoscopic devices appeared. First among these were arthroscopes for orthopedic surgery, available in most large hospitals by 1975, but at that point more a gimmick than a mainstream procedure. Safe surgical procedures with such scopes were limited because the surgeon had to operate while holding the scope in one hand and a single instrument in the other.

The introduction of the small medical video camera attachable to the eyepiece of the arthroscope or laparoscope changed the image of endoscopy in the mind of the surgical community and turned arthroscopy, cholecystectomy—removal of the gallbladder with instruments inserted through the abdominal wall—and numerous other microsurgical procedures into common operative procedures by the early 1990s.

Surgeons in France and the US built upon this technology by developing new, specialized instruments for tissue handling, cutting, and hemostasis. Due to their benefits of small scars, less pain, and a more rapid recovery, endoscopic procedures were rapidly adopted after the late 1980s and becoming a standard method for nearly every area of surgery in the 1990s. Demand from patients has

had much to do with the rapid evolution of the technology. Equally important have been the efforts of health care organizations to control costs. In a period of deep concern about skyrocketing healthcare costs, any procedure that improved surgical outcomes and reduced hospital stays interested medical instrument makers. Encouraged by the success of the new videoendoscopic devices, medical instrument companies in the early 1990s foresaw a new field of minimally invasive diagnostic and surgical tools. Surgery was about to enter a technology-intense era that offered immense opportunities to companies teaming surgeons and engineers to apply the latest developments in robotics, imaging, and sensing to the field of minimally invasive surgery. While pathbreaking developments had occurred, the instruments available for such surgeries allowed only a limited number of the complex functions demanded by the surgeon. Surgeons needed better visualization, finer manipulators, and new types of remote sensors, and they needed these tools integrated into a complete system.

TELEPRESENCE SURGERY

A new vision emerged, heavily nurtured by funds from the Advanced Research Projects Agency (ARPA), the NIH, and NASA, and developed through contracts made by these agencies to laboratories such as Stanford Research Institute (SRI), Johns Hopkins Institute for Information Enhanced Medicine, University of North Carolina Computer Science Department, the University of Washington Human Interface Technology Laboratory, the Mayo Clinic, and the MIT Artificial Intelligence Laboratory. The vision promoted by Dr. Richard Satava, who spearheaded the ARPA program, was to develop “telepresence” workstations that would allow surgeons to perform telerobotically complex surgical procedures that demand great dexterity. These workstations would recreate and magnify all of the motor, visual, and sensory sensations of the surgeon as if he were he actually inside the patient. The aim of the programs sponsored by these agencies was eventually to enable surgeons to perform surgeries, such as certain complex brain surgeries or heart operations not even possible in the early 1990s, improve the speed and surety of existing procedures, and reduce the number of people in the surgical team. Central to this program was telepresence-telerobotics, allowing an operator the complex sensory feedback and motor control he would have if he were actually at the work site, carrying out the operation with his own hands. The goal of telepresence was to project full motor and sensory capabilities—visual, tactile, force, auditory—into even microscopic environments to perform operations that demand fine dexterity and hand-eye coordination.

Philip Green led a team at SRI that assembled the first working model of a telepresence surgery system in 1991, and with funding from the NIH Green went on to design and build a demonstration system. The proposal contained the diagram

shown in Fig. 1,⁴ showing the concept of workstation, viewing arrangement, and manipulation configuration used in the surgical telepresence systems today. In 1992 SRI obtained funding for a second-generation telepresence system for emergency surgeries in battlefield situations. For this second-generation system the SRI team developed the precise servo-mechanics, force-feedback, 3-D visualization and surgical instruments needed to build a computer-driven system that could accurately reproduce a surgeon's hand motions with remote surgical instruments having 5-degrees of freedom and extremely sensitive tactile response.

In late 1995 SRI licensed this technology to Intuitive Surgical, Inc. of Mountain View, CA. Intuitive Surgical furthered the work begun at SRI by improving on the precise control of the surgical instruments, adding a new invention, EndoWrist™, patented by company cofounder Frederic Moll, which added two degrees of freedom to the SRI device—inner pitch and inner yaw (Inner pitch is the motion a wrist performs to knock on a door; inner yaw is the side-to-side movement used in wiping a table)—allowing the system to better mimic a surgeon's actions; it gives the robot ability to reach around, beyond and behind delicate body structures, delivering these angles right at the surgical site. Through licenses of IBM patents, Intuitive also improved the 3-D video imaging, navigation and registration of the video image to the spatial frame in which the robot operates. The system employs 250 megaflops of parallel processing power.

A further crucial improvement to the system was brought by Kenneth Salisbury from the MIT Artificial Intelligence Laboratory who imported ideas from the force-reflecting haptic feedback system he and Thomas Massie invented as the basis of their PHANTOM™⁵ system, a device invented in 1993 permitting touch interactions between human users and remote virtual and physical environments. The PHANTOM™ is a desktop device which provides a force-reflecting interface between a human user and a computer. Users connect to the mechanism by simply inserting their index finger into a thimble. The PHANTOM™ tracks the motion of the user's finger tip and can actively exert an external force on the finger, creating compelling illusions of interaction with solid physical objects. A stylus can be substituted for the thimble and users can feel the tip of the stylus touch virtual surfaces. The haptic interface allows the system to go beyond previous instruments for minimally invasive surgery (MIS). These instruments preclude a sense of touch or feeling for the surgeon; the PHANTOM™ haptic interface, by contrast, gives an additional element of immersion. When the arm encounters resistance inside the patient, that resistance is transmitted back to the console, where the surgeon can feel it. When the thimble hits a position corresponding to the surface of a virtual object in the computer, three motors generate forces on the thimble that imitate the feel of the object. The PHANTOM™ can duplicate

⁴Insert diagram from *Time Magazine*, Special Issue, Fall, 1996.

⁵Insert image of PHANTOM™ from SensAble Technologies.

all sorts of textures, including coarse, slippery, spongy, or even sticky surfaces. It also reproduces friction. And if two PHANToM™s are put together a user can ‘grab’ a virtual object with thumb and forefinger. Given advanced haptic and visual feedback, the system greatly facilitates dissecting, cutting, suturing and other surgical procedures, even those on very small structures, by giving the doctor inches to move in order to cut millimeters. Furthermore, it can be programmed to compensate for error and natural hand tremors that would otherwise negatively affect MIS technique.

The surgical manipulator made its first public debut in actual surgery in May of 1998. From May through December 1998 Professor Alain Carpentier and Dr. Didier Loulmet of the Broussais Hospital in Paris performed six open heart surgeries using the Intuitive™ system.⁶ In June of 1998 the same team performed the world’s first closed-chest video-endoscopic coronary bypass surgery completely through small (1-cm) ports in the chest wall. Since that time more than 250 heart surgeries and 150 completely video-endoscopic surgeries have been performed with the system. The system was given approval to be sold throughout the European Community in January of 1999.

MEDICAL AVATARS

Such examples demonstrate that computational modeling has added an entirely new dimension to surgery. For the first time the surgeon is able to plan and simulate a surgery based on a mathematical model that reflects the actual anatomy and physiology of the individual patient. Moreover, the model need not stay outside the operating room. Several groups of researchers have used these models to develop “augmented reality” systems that produce a precise, scaleable registration of the model on the patient so that a fusion of the model and the 3D stereo camera images is made. This procedure has been carried out successfully in removing brain tumors and in a number of prostatectomies in the Mayo Clinic’s Virtual Reality Assisted Surgery Program (VRASP) headed by Richard Robb.⁷

In addition to improving the performance of surgeons by putting predictive modeling and mathematically precise planning at their disposal, computers are playing a major role in improving surgical outcomes by providing surgeons opportunities to train and rehearse important procedures before they go into the operating theater. By 1995 modeling and planning systems began to be implemented in both surgical training simulators and in real time surgeries. One of the first systems to incorporate all these features in a surgical simulator was developed for eye surgery by MIT robotics scientist Ian Hunter. Hunter’s microsurgical robot (MSR) system incorporated features

⁶Insert images of Intuitive Surgical DaVinci System and Dr. Carpentier surgery.

⁷Insert picture of data fusion from VRASP.

described above such as data acquisition by CT and MRI scanning, use of finite element modeling of the planned surgical procedure, a force-reflecting haptic feedback system which enables the perception of tissue cutting forces, including those that would normally be imperceptible to the surgeon if they were transmitted directly to his hands.

A distinctive feature of Hunter’s MSR is its immersive virtual environment which fuses video, touch, and sound into a virtual reality experience.⁸ The haptic environment in Hunter’s system is fused with 3D stereo camera images fed to a head-mounted display. As if in a flight simulator the surgeon can rehearse his procedure on the model of the individual patient he has constructed. In addition, the model can be used as a training site for student surgeons, co-present during a practice surgery, sharing the same video screen and feeling the same surgical moves as the master surgeon.⁹ But such systems can also be deployed in a collaborative telesurgery system, allowing different specialists to be faded in to “take the controls” during different parts of the procedure. Indeed, a “collaborative clinic” incorporating these features was demonstrated at NASA-Ames on May 5, 1999 with participants at five different sites around the US.

BIOLOGY IN SILICO

Two different styles of work have characterized the field of molecular biology since the late 1960s. The biophysical approach has sought to predict the function of a molecule from its structure. The biochemical approach, on the other hand, has been concerned with predicting phenotype from biochemical function. If there has been a unifying framework for the field, at least from its early days up through the 1980s, it was provided by the “central dogma” emerging from the work of Watson, Crick, Monod, and Jacob in the late 1960s, schematized as follows:

DNA □ RNA □ Protein □□□□ Function

In terms of the “central dogma” the measure of success in the enterprise of making biology predictive would be—and has been since the days of Claude Bernard—rational medicine. If one had a complete grasp of all the levels from DNA to behavioral function including the processes of translation at each level, then one could target specific proteins or biochemical processes that may be malfunctioning and design drugs specifically to repair these disorders. For molecular biologists with high theory ambitions the preferred path toward achieving

⁸Insert image of Ian Hunter’s microsurgical robot system. (from *Presence*, vol. 2, and MIT Robotics website).

⁹Insert figure from Hunter, et al. *Presence*, vol 2, showing “fade in” of student surgeons.

this goal has been based on the notion that the function of a molecule is determined by its three-dimensional folding and that the structure of proteins is uniquely contained in the linear sequence of their amino acids.¹⁰ But determination of protein structure and function is only part of the problem confronting a theoretical biology. A fully-fledged theoretical biology would want to be able to determine the biochemical function of the protein structure as well as its expected behavioral contribution within the organism. Thus biochemists have resisted the road of high theory and have pursued a solidly experimental approach aimed at eliciting common models of biochemical function across a range of mid-level biological structures from proteins and enzymes through cells. Their approach has been to identify a gene by some direct experimental procedure—determined by some property of its product or otherwise related to its phenotype—to clone it, to sequence, it, to make its product and to continue to work experimentally so as to seek an understanding of its function. This model, as Walter Gilbert has observed, was suited to “small science,” experimental science conducted in a single lab.¹¹

The emergence of organizations like the Brookhaven Protein Data Bank in 1971, GenBank in 1982, and BIONET in 1984, and the massive amount of sequencing data that began to become available in university and company databases, and more recently publicly through the Human Genome Initiative, have complicated this picture immensely through an unprecedented influx of new data. In the process a paradigm shift has occurred in both the intellectual and institutional structures of biology. According to some of the central players in this transformation, at the core is biology’s switch from having been an observational science, limited primarily by the ability to make observations, to being a data-bound science limited by its practitioner’s ability to understand large amounts of information derived from observations. To understand the data the tools of information science have not only become necessary handmaidens to theory: they have also fundamentally changed the picture of biological theory itself. A new picture of theory radically different from even the biophysicists’ model of theory has come into view. Disciplinarily, biology has become an information science. Institutionally it is becoming “big science.” Gilbert characterizes the situation sharply:

To use this flood of knowledge, which will pour across the computer networks of the world, biologists not only must become computer-literate, but also change their approach to the problem of understanding life.

¹⁰See Christian B. Anfinsen, “Principles that Govern the Folding of Protein Chains.” *Science* (1973). 181(Number 4096): 223-230 discusses the work for which he was awarded the Nobel Prize for Chemistry in 1972: “This hypothesis (the “thermodynamic hypothesis”) states that the three-dimensional structure of a native protein in its normal physiological milieu...is the one in which the Gibbs free energy of the whole system is lowest; that is, that the totality of interatomic interactions and hence by the amino acid sequence, in a given environment.” (p. 223)

¹¹Walter Gilbert, “Towards a Paradigm Shift in Biology,” *Nature*, 349 (1991), p. 99.

The next tenfold increase in the amount of information in the databases will divide the world into haves and have-nots, unless each of us connects to that information and learns how to sift through it for the parts we need.¹²

The new data-bound biology Gilbert hints at in this scenario is genomics, the theoretical component of which might be termed “computational biology,” while its instrumental and experimental component might be considered as “bioinformatics.” The fundamental dogma of this new biology, as characterized by Douglas Brutlag, reformulates the central dogma of Jacob-Monod in terms of “information flow”:¹³

Genetic information	□	Molecular structure	□□□□□	Biochemical function	□□□□	Biologic behavior
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Walter Gilbert described the newly forming genomic view of biology in 1991:

The new paradigm now emerging is that all the “genes” will be known (in the sense of being resident in databases available electronically), and that the starting point of a biological investigation will be theoretical. An individual scientist will begin with a theoretical conjecture, only then turning to experiment to follow or test that hypothesis. The actual biology will continue to be done as “small science”—depending on individual insight and inspiration to produce new knowledge—but the reagents that the scientist uses will include a knowledge of the primary sequence of the organism, together with a list of all previous deductions from that sequence.¹⁴ Genomics, computational biology, and bioinformatics restructure the playing field of biology bringing a substantially modified toolkit to the repertoire of molecular biology skills developed in the 1970s. Along with the biochemistry components new skills are now required, including machine learning, robotics, databases, statistics and probability, artificial intelligence, information theory, algorithms, and graph theory.¹⁵

Proclamations of the sort made by Gilbert and other promoters of genomics may seem like hyperbole. But the Human Genome Initiative and the information technology that enables it has changed molecular biology in fundamental ways, and indeed, may suggest similar changes in store for other domains of science. The online DNA and protein databases I have described have not just been repositories of

¹²Ibid.

¹³Douglas L. Brutlag, “Understanding the Human Genome,” in P. Leder, D.A. Clayton, and E. Rubenstein, eds., *Scientific American: Introduction to Molecular Medicine*, New York; Scientific American, Inc., 1994, p. 153-168.

¹⁴Walter Gilbert, “Towards a Paradigm Shift in Biology,” *Nature*, 349 (1991), p. 99.

¹⁵These are the disciplines graduate students and postdocs in molecular biology in Brutlag’s lab at Stanford are expected to work with. Source: Douglas Brutlag, “Department Review: Bioinformatics Group, Department of Biochemistry, Stanford University, 1998,” personal communication.

information for insertion into the routine work of molecular biology, and the software programs used to interact with this data are more than retrieval aids for transporting that information back to the lab. We need to attend in more detail to some of the ways this software has been used to address the problems of molecular biology in order to gain a sense of the changes taking place.

A dramatic illustration of how sequence alignment tools can be brought to bear on determining function and structure is provided by the case of cystic fibrosis. Cystic fibrosis is caused by aberrant regulation of chloride transport across epithelial cells in the pulmonary tree, the intestine, the exocrine pancreas, and apocrine sweat glands. This disorder was identified as due to defects in the cystic fibrosis transmembrane conductance regulator protein (CFTR). The CFTR gene was isolated in 1989, and subsequently identified as producing a chloride channel whose activity depends on phosphorylation of particular residues within the regulatory region of the protein. Using computer-based sequence alignment tools of the sort described above, it was established that a consensus sequence for nucleotide binding folds that bind ATP are present near the regulatory region and that 70 percent of cystic fibrosis mutations are accounted for by a 3 base-pair deletion that removes a phenylalanine residue within the first nucleotide binding position. A significant portion of the remainder of cystic fibrosis mutations affect a second nucleotide-binding domain near the regulatory region.¹⁶

In working out the folds and binding domains for the CFTR protein Hyde, Emsley, Hartshorn, et al. (1990) used sequence alignment methods similar to those available in early models of the IntelliGenetics software suite.¹⁷ In 1992 IntelliGenetics introduced BLAZE, an even more rapid search program running on a massively parallel computer. As an example of how computational genomics can be used to solve structure-function problems in molecular biology, Brutlag repeated the CFTR case using BLAZE.¹⁸ A sequence similarity search compared the CFTR protein to more

¹⁶S. C. Hyde, P. Emsley, *et al.* (1990). "Structural Model of ATP-binding Proteins Associated with Cystic fibrosis, Multidrug Resistance and Bacterial Transport." *Nature* 346: 362-365; B.S. Kerem, J. M. Rommens, et al. "Identification of the Cystic Fibrosis Gene: Genetic Analysis," *Science* 245(1989): 1073-1080; B. S. Kerem, J. Zielenski, et al. "Identification of Mutations in Regions Corresponding to the Two Putative Nucleotide (ATP)-Binding Folds of the Cystic Fibrosis Gene," *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 87(1990): 8447-8451; J. R. Riordan, J. M. Rommens, *et al.*, "Identification of the Cystic Fibrosis Gene: Cloning and Characterization of Complementary RNA," *Science* 245(1989): 1066-1073.

¹⁷Hyde, Emsley, *et al.* used the Chou-Fasman algorithm (1973) for identifying consensus sequences and the Quantatm modeling package produced by Polygen Corp., Waltham, Mass. for modeling the protein and its binding sites. See, S. C. Hyde, P. Emsley, *et al.* (1990). "Structural Model of ATP-binding Proteins Associated with Cystic fibrosis, Multidrug Resistance and Bacterial Transport." *Nature* 346: 362-365.

¹⁸D. Brutlag, "Understanding the Human Genome" *Scientific American Introduction to Molecular Medicine*. P. Leder, D. A. Clayton and E. Rubenstein, Eds. New York, NY, Scientific American, Inc., 1994: p. 164-166.

than 26,000 proteins in a protein database of more than 9 million residues, resulting in a list of 27 top similar proteins, all of which strongly suggested the CFTR protein is a membrane protein involved in secretion. Another feature of the comparison result was that significant homologies were shown with ATP-binding transport proteins, further strengthening the identification of CFTR as a membrane protein. The search algorithm identified two consensus sequence motifs in the protein sequence of the cystic fibrosis gene product that corresponded to the two sites on the protein involved in binding nucleotides. The search also turned up distant homologies between the CFTR protein and proteins of *E. coli* and yeast. The entire search took three hours. Such examples offer convincing evidence that tools of computational molecular biology can lead to the understanding of protein function.

The methods for analyzing sequence data discussed above were just the beginnings of an explosion of database mining tools for genomics that is continuing to take place.¹⁹ In the process biology is becoming even more aptly characterized as an information science.²⁰ Advances in the field have led to large-scale automation of sequencing in genome centers employing robots. The success this large-scale sequencing of genes has enjoyed has in turn spawned a similar approach to applying automation to sequencing proteins, a new area complementary to genomics called proteomics. Similar in concept to genomics, which seeks to identify all genes,

¹⁹See for instance the National Institute of General Medical Science, “(NIGMS), Protein Structure Initiative Meeting Summary,” April 24, 1998, at: http://www.nih.gov/nigms/news/reports/protein_structure.html

²⁰I have focused on the development of software in this discussion. But a further crucial stimulation to the takeoff of bioinformatics, of course, are hardware and networking developments. The growth of databases and complexity of the searches that were to be undertaken stimulated the demand for faster algorithms, more powerful computer systems, and network bandwidth. At the beginning of this “bioinformatics revolution” in the 1970s, for example, a search on a DNA sequence of typical size would be performed by a computer capable of performing one million instructions per second (one MIP) and would take approximately 15 minutes. Throughout the late 1970s and 1980s mini-computers and personal computer workstations continued to increase in power at about the same rate as the growth of the databases, so that a typical search still took around 15 minutes. By the end of the 1980s, however, the growth in sequence data—now hundreds of megabytes in size—had overtaken the ability of computers to search it with acceptable turnaround time. Shortcut search methods and more efficient code helped, but the most rigorous and sensitive searches began to require hours of computing time to align and score even a single query sequence against a database of sequences. The NIH and NSF responded to the challenge by supporting research and development of new computer architectures, regional supercomputer centers and several large-scale computing initiatives. (see Thomas P. Hughes, et al., ed., *Funding a Revolution: Government Support for Computing Research*, Washington, D.C., National Academy Press, 1999.) Commercial vendors such as DEC, SUN Microsystems, Cray Computers, and MasPar Computer Corporation tried to meet the large-scale computing needs of geneticists with, for example, massively parallel computers, such as the MasPar MP-1 computer. In early 1992, the MasPar MP-1104 with 4,096 processors could search the entire Swiss-Protein database in 30 seconds with a query of 100 amino acids, and a query of 1000 amino acids could be executed on the GenBank database (74,000 sequences) in 15 minutes. (see IntelliGenetics, Inc., and MasPar Computer corporation, “BLAZE: A Massively Parallel Sequence Similarity Search Program for Molecular Biologists,” Product Information Bulletin, May 1992.)

proteomics aims to develop techniques that can rapidly identify the type, amount and activities of the thousands of proteins in a cell. Indeed, new biotechnology companies have started marketing technologies and services for mining protein information en masse. Oxford Glycosciences (OGS) in Abingdon, England, has automated the laborious technique of two-dimensional gel electrophoresis.²¹ In the OGS process, an electric current applied to a sample on a polymer gel separates the proteins, first by their unique electric charge characteristics and then by size. A dye attaches to each separated protein arrayed across the gel. Then a digital imaging device automatically detects protein levels by how much the dye fluoresces. Each of the 5,000 to 6,000 proteins that may be assayed in a sample in the course of a few days is channeled through a mass spectrometer that determines its amino acid sequence. The identity of the protein can be determined by comparing the amino acid sequence with information contained in numerous gene and protein databases. One imaged array of proteins can be contrasted with another to find proteins specific to a disease.

In order to keep pace with this flood of data emerging from automated sequencing, genome researchers have in turn looked increasingly to artificial intelligence, machine learning, and even robotics in developing automated methods for discovering patterns and protein motifs from sequence data. The power of these methods is their ability both to represent structural features rather than strictly evolutionary steps and to discover motifs from sequences automatically. The methods developed in the field of machine learning have been used to extract conserved residues, discover pairs of correlated residues, and find higher order relationships between residues as well. Techniques from the field of machine learning have included perceptrons, discriminant analysis, neural networks, Bayesian networks, hidden Markov models, minimal length encoding, and context-free grammars.²² Important methods for evaluating and validating novel protein motifs have also derived from the machine learning area.

Many molecular biologists who welcomed the Human Genome Initiative with open arms undoubtedly believed that when the genome was sequenced everyone would return to the lab to conduct their experiments in a business-as-usual fashion, empowered with a richer set of fundamental data. The developments in automation, the resulting explosion of data, and the introduction of tools of information science to master this data have changed the playing field forever: there may be no “lab” to return to. In its place is a workstation hooked to a massively parallel computer, producing simulations by drawing on the data streams of the major databanks and carrying out “experiments” *in silico* rather than *in vitro*. The result of biology’s metamorphosis into an information science just may be the relocation of the lab to the industrial park and the dustbin of history.

²¹See the discussion of this technology at the NIGMS site listed in note 81 as well as at the site of Oxford Glycosciences: <http://www.ogs.com/proteome/home.html>

²²See especially the papers in L. Hunter, ed., *Artificial Intelligence and Molecular Biology*, Menlo Park, CA, AAAI Press, 1993.

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